

TÜRKMENISTANYŇ BILIM MINISTRRLIGI
TÜRKMENISTANYŇ YLYMLAR AKADEMIÝASY
MINISTRY OF EDUCATION OF TURKMENISTAN
ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF TURKMENISTAN
МИНИСТЕРСТВО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ ТУРКМЕНИСТАНА
АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК ТУРКМЕНИСТАНА

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YLMY HYÝALBENTLIGIŇ HÄZIRKI YLMY-TEHNIKI ÖSÜŞLERE TÄSIRI

Ylmy hyýalbentlik diňe bir medeniýete we jemgyýete däl, eýsem ylmy we tehnologiýa ösüş-de uly täsir edýär. Ylmy fantastika ýazyjylarynyň oýlap tapyşlary we enjamlary, käte hatda manysyz hem hasaplanýar, häzirki zaman senagatynda we ylym talap edýän ugurlarda işjeň ulanylýar. Häzirki zaman jemgyýetiniň ylmy-tehniki düzümine täsiri iki ýagdaý sebäpli has hem artdy. Birinjiden, ylmy fantastika edebi çäklerden daşarda oýun we kino pudagyna giňeldi. Häzirki wagtda käbir tehniki oýlap tapyşlaryň we enjamlaryň meşhurlygynyň, kompýuter oýunlarynda we bazary emele getirýän filmlerde görkezilmegine we hakykatdan hem käbir ugurlarda ylmy-tehniki ösüşe gönükdirilendigi äşgärdir. Ikinjiden, döredijilik we ylmy ugurlaryň arasynda ýüze çykan has ýakyn hyzmatdaşlyk. Ösen ýurtlaryň köpüsünde, netijeli bilelikdäki taslamalaryň ýüze çykmagy bilen aň-bilim ulgamynyň wekilleri bilen alymlaryň arasynda işjeň täsirleşmek meýli bar. Şeýlelik bilen, häzirki wagtda ylmy fantastika adamyň işjeňliginiň ylmy-tehniki gurşawyny ösdürmekdäki ornuna üns bermezlik mümkin däl we oňa has çynlakaý we giňişleýin garamak zerur.

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IMPACT OF SCIENCE FICTION ON MODERN SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL PROGRESS

Science fiction has a huge impact not only on culture and society, but also on scientific and technological progress. The inventions and devices of science fiction writers, sometimes considered even as an absurd, are now actively used in modern industry and science-intensive fields. The influence on scientific-technical component of modern society has increased even more due to the two factors. Firstly, the expansion of science fiction beyond literary borders into the gaming and film industries. It is obvious that today the popularity of certain technical inventions and devices directly depends on their coverage in computer games and movies shaping the market and actually directing scientific-technical development in certain fields. Secondly, the closer collaboration that has emerged between creative and scientific areas. In most highly developed countries, there is an obvious tendency for active

interaction between representatives of the sci-fi genre and scientists, expressed by the emergence of fruitful joint projects. Thus, today it is no longer possible to ignore the role of science fiction in the development of scientific-technical sphere of human activity and it is necessary to take it more seriously and broadly.

Science fiction as a literary genre is generated by the multifaceted interaction of artistic creativity with science. It is reflected in works of Isaac Asimov, Gary Raham, Brian Stableford, Thomas Michaud, Peter Bowler, Barry Luokkala and many other scientists, literary critics, philosophers and writers. But as Anatoly Britikov accurately notes, science fiction was “nourished by the mistress of poetry Euterpa together with the muse of astronomy Urania” [7, 34]. Science fiction motifs are rooted in ancient Assyro-Babylonian, Indian, Chinese, Arabic and Iranian epos, but it is the novel by Edgar Poe “The Unparalleled Adventure of One Hans Pfaall” (1835) that literary critics note as the starting point for a new type of literature, and it is the dilogy by Jules Verne “From the Earth to the Moon” (1865) and “Round the Moon” (1867) that is considered as the birthplace of the science fiction genre in its modern form. Classic science fiction (Herbert Wells, Ray Bradbury, Arthur Clark, Isaac Asimov, Ivan Efremov etc.) tries to predict the future, while in modern science fiction (Peter Watts, Cixin Liu, Karl Schroeder, John Scalzi, Stephen Baxter etc.), the grandiose process of development of science-intensive spheres of human activity finds its frontal reflection. Until recently, science fiction did not set itself such versatile tasks, did not connect so closely such a number of scientific disciplines.

Contemporary artistic creation expresses itself in a science fiction novel not as a simple illustration, not as a servant of scientific thought. Science fiction makes its own original contribution to the scientific and public consciousness. At the junction of artistic and scientific creativity, it puts forward the criterion of the humanistic expediency of those ideas and concepts, conceivable directions of technological progress that appear on the horizon of the future. Modern science fiction “influences scientific, technical and social processes”. A science fiction novel creates such an artistic world that its plausibility is believed to have a mythologizing effect in non-literary discussions about the feasibility of certain ideas. Science fiction carries out “fine-tuning” and puts new ideas and hypotheses into the widest circulation. A complex and fruitful interchange of dynamic scientific ideas with inertial everyday ones takes place in it; both are, as it were, mutually tested for truth. Interdependence between the level of development of science-intensive technologies and the level of development of science fiction literature in a particular country can be observed. In fact, Russia, USA, China, Japan, Great Britain, France, India, Germany are the leading countries in the

rankings in terms of the level of development of science and the volume of published science fiction works.

Thus, modern science fiction can serve as an example of the impact of science on literature, as well as the deep penetration of artistic creativity into the scientific-technical sphere. Just as non-fantastic literature has become a part of social thought in the knowledge of the present and the past, science fiction has grown into an effective tool for influencing scientific and technological progress, all the more effective because it acts on behalf of the mass consciousness and appeals to it at the same time.

Рафаэль Ахмедов
(Узбекистан)

ВЛИЯНИЕ НАУЧНОЙ ФАНТАСТИКИ НА СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ ПРОГРЕСС

Научная фантастика оказывает заметное влияние не только на культуру и общество, но и на научно-технический прогресс. Разработки писателей-фантастов, считавшиеся выдумкой и даже абсурдом, активно применяются в современной промышленности и наукоемких сферах деятельности. Влияние на научно-техническую составляющую современного общества ещё более усилилось благодаря двум факторам. Во-первых, благодаря расширению научной фантастики за границы литературы в сферы игро- и киноиндустрии. Очевидно, что сегодня популярность тех или иных технических разработок и изобретений напрямую зависит от их освещения в компьютерных играх и фильмах, что не только формирует рынок, но и фактически направляет научно-техническое развитие в определенное русло. Второй фактор – более тесное сотрудничество, возникшее между творческой и научной сферами. В развитых странах очевидна тенденция активного взаимодействия между представителями научно-фантастического жанра и учеными, выраженного появлением совместных плодотворных проектов.

Таким образом, сегодня уже невозможно игнорировать роль научной фантастики в развитии научно-технической сферы человеческой деятельности и необходимо воспринимать её более серьёзно и обширно.

Артем Гаврилов ОБ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ ЭКСПРЕССИВНЫХ СИНТАКСИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ В СЕТЕВЫХ ГАЗЕТНЫХ ЗАГОЛОВКАХ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ РАЗНОСТРУКТУРНЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ)	91
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